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Problems Encountered by Mëranao Selected Teachers in the Implementation of Mother Tongue among Public Schools in Lanao del Norte: Its Implication

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Introduction

The MTB-MLE program implemented in the Philippines has been one of the major educational reforms aiming at providing literate learning outcomes among the various linguistic groups in the country. However, in Lanao del Norte where Meranao language is the most widely spoken dialect, challenges have emerged for the teachers in effectively delivering mother tongue instruction. Among the many potential advantages of teaching through a mother tongue approach, several challenges bar its effective implementation.

Studies indicate that language is an essential component of instruction because it allows for deeper comprehension and engagement by students (Gonzalez, 2015). However, teaching practitioners in Meranao affirmed that inadequate training, limited infrastructures, and shabby services provided by the community hinder effective instructions in the native language (Salvador, 2018). Socio-political considerations like ethnic conflict and economic inequality further complicate the educational landscape of Lanao del Norte (Magsino, 2020).

Background of the Study

The implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) program in the Philippines has been a significant educational reform aimed at improving literacy and learning outcomes among diverse linguistic groups. In Lanao del Norte, where the Meranao language is predominantly spoken, teachers face unique challenges in effectively delivering instruction in the mother tongue. Despite the potential benefits of this approach, various obstacles hinder its successful implementation.

Research indicates that language plays a crucial role in education, particularly in enhancing comprehension and engagement among students (Gonzalez, 2015). However, Meranao teachers report difficulties related to inadequate training, limited resources, and a lack of community support, which can impede the effective delivery of instruction in the mother tongue (Salvador, 2018).

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This study aims to explore the specific problems encountered by selected Meranao teachers in implementing the MTB-MLE program in public schools and to analyze the implications of these challenges for educational policy and practice. By examining these issues, this research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in mother tongue education and to propose actionable solutions that can enhance its effectiveness in the region.

Theoretical Framework

In any research, theories, concepts and paradigms are essential to support the ideas presented in the paper. Basically, they serve as a way to complete the idea of the paper it wants to prove.

This study draws upon two primary theoretical frameworks to understand the problems encountered by Meranao teachers in implementing mother tongue education in Lanao del Norte:

(1) The Theory of Language Acquisition and (2) The Social-Ecological Model of Development.

1. Theory of Language Acquisition:

This theory, rooted in the work of linguists like Noam Chomsky and Stephen Krashen, emphasizes the crucial role of the first language in cognitive development and learning. It posits that children acquire language naturally through exposure and interaction, and that their native language serves as a foundation for acquiring other languages (Krashen, 1985). This framework is relevant to this study because it highlights the potential benefits of using the Meranao language as the primary medium of instruction in early childhood education. By providing a familiar and accessible language environment, Meranao students can develop stronger cognitive skills and a deeper understanding of their cultural heritage.

2. The Social-Ecological Model of Development:

This model, developed by Urie Bronfenbrenner. This framework is relevant to this study because it recognizes the complex interplay of factors that impact the success of mother tongue education. For instance, the availability of appropriate teaching materials, the support of school administrators, and the attitudes of parents towards the Meranao language all contribute to the challenges faced by Meranao teachers in implementing the program.

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Figure 1. Research Paradigm.

Figure 1. shows the research paradigm of the study. This paradigm emphasizes understanding the lived experiences and perspectives of Meranao teachers regarding the implementation of MTB-MLE. It aims to uncover the complexities and nuances of their challenges, motivations, and beliefs surrounding the policy.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the problems encountered by Meranao Selected Teachers in the Implementation of Mother Tongue among Selected Public Schools in Lanao del Norte. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the personal profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Teaching Position;
 - 1.4 Years in Teaching;

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- 1.5 Assigned Year Level;
- 1.6 Highest Educational Attainment;
- 1.7 Monthly Income;
- 1.8 Status of Appointment;
2. What is the level of implementation of the MTB-MLE?
3. What are the problems encountered by the respondents in the Implementation of Mother Tongue as Their Medium of Classroom Instruction in terms of:
 - 2.1 Language Learning
 - 2.2 Classroom Instruction
4. Is there a significant relationship between students the level of implementation when grouped according to profile?
5. What implications can be drawn from the findings?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between students the level of implementation when grouped according to profile

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study is in relation to the use of Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Education as a subject matter and as a medium of instruction inside the classroom from Kindergarten to Grade 3 level. The focus of this study is to determining the Problems Encountered by Meranao teachers in the implementation of Mother Tongue. This is to verify if the teachers' teaching styles match with the pupils' learning styles.

The respondents of this study were the kindergarten, Grade I, II, III teachers of Primary and Elementary Selected Schools in Lanao del Norte. The Grade IV, V, VI teachers are not included in this study since they are not required to use Mother Tongue as a subject matter and as medium of instruction.

Definition of Terms

Some terms need to be both operationally and conceptually defined in the interest of greater clarity and common understanding among readers from diverse backgrounds or fields.

Achievement. This refers to ability or skills developed as result of learning. Achievement is measured by an achievement test which is syllabus- or material-bound (Davies, 1994). In this study, it is used in the same sense, or more specifically, as a measure of one's performance.

Bilingual Education. This refers to the use of two languages in a formal educational system (UNESCO, 2010). In this study, this refers to the two official languages used in teaching-learning interaction, and that were the Filipino and English.

Curriculum. It is a teaching plan, content and instructional materials for an education program (cited by Ball, 2010). In this study, this refers to the learning content of the pupils throughout the school year from kindergarten to Grade 12 contained of K-12 curriculum.

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Medium of Instruction. This refers to the language used in teaching. The medium of instruction is usually an officially recognized languages, such as Filipino and English. In this study, it refers to language(s) being taught and applied to help facilitate the learning process.

Multilingual Education (MLE). This is a formal use of more than two languages for literacy and instruction. This begins with developing L1 and gradually adding other languages (UNESCO, 2010). Multilingual Education often includes the L1, the national language, and a language of a wider communication (Burton, 2013). In the context of this study, the language includes Meranao, Filipino and English.

Pupils. In this study, they are referred to as the recipients of Mother Tongue-Based instruction.

Theoretical Framework

The most effective theoretical framework will depend on the specific research questions and objectives. It is likely that a combination of these frameworks will be necessary to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by Meranao teachers in implementing MTB-MLE. For example, a combination of sociocultural theory and language policy and planning could be used to examine the relationship between language use, cultural identity, and policy implementation.

By carefully selecting and applying a relevant theoretical framework, this research can contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities of implementing MTB-MLE in the Philippines and potentially inform strategies for improving its effectiveness.
Statement of the Problem

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive method of research which is fact-finding with adequate interpretation. It is something beyond just data-gathering but the present facts are also involved.

Research Locale and Respondents

The study was conducted at Lanao del Norte it is situated in Northern Mindanao, along the northwest and southwest coast of the Mindanao Island. Its boundaries include Iligan Bay on the North, the provinces of Lanao del Sur and Bukidnon to the East, Illana Bay and the Celebes Sea to the South and Southwest, and the province of Zamboanga del Sur and Panguil Bay to the West, with the province of Misamis Occidental on the opposite side of Panguil Bay. The research subjects of this study are the elementary teachers from selected public schools in the Lanao del Norte. Specifically, the researcher will select 100 teachers through convenient sampling. They were given the corresponding questionnaires to gather accurate information.

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Research Instruments

The researcher made use a self-made questionnaire, written primarily in English, as an instrument in gathering data and information needed in the study. A questionnaire gathers data faster than any other method. Besides, the respondents could read and answer the questionnaires with ease.

The questionnaire was composed of two parts. Part I is aimed to gather information on the respondent's personal profile such as age, gender, religion, academic status. Part II dealt with the respondents' responses about the Difficulties and strategies in the Implementation of Mother Tongue as Medium of Instruction met by Meranao Teachers.

Data Gathering Procedure

The primary data was taken from the responses of respondents through questionnaire that was distributed and collected by the researcher themselves among the selected elementary teachers and a follow-up interview of some relevant information from them. In addition, the data gathered focused on the level of knowledge of the respondents regarding the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) policy. The instructional materials used by the teachers, the preferred medium of instruction of the teachers, the challenges faced by the teachers in using mother tongue as medium of instruction, and the recommendation of the teachers for the improvement of the implementation of the said policy.

Statistical Tools Used

The data collected was analyzed purely descriptive in nature. A tabular presentation used that includes the frequency and percentage columns in analyzing the data. Frequency percentage and rank distribution were utilized in tabulating and analyzing the data.

References

The study references a wide range of sources, including academic articles, journals, and research papers that aims to contribute to the ongoing discussion of MTB-MLE challenges, specifically addressing the unique experiences of Meranao teachers in Lanao del Norte, and exploring the implications for language revitalization, student learning, and educational equity.

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